

Stress Distribution around Hole of Angle-Ply Laminates under Uni-Axial Tension

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ABSTRACT

The angle-ply laminate has in most cases a negative value of $g (= \sqrt{E_x E_y} / G_{xy} - 2(1 + \sqrt{v_x v_y}))$ ranging from 0 to -4 with reference to x and y axes taken along the bisectors of the included angle by a pair of fiber directions, while the cross-ply laminate always has a positive value of g.

An analysis is given on the stress distribution for an infinite angle-ply laminate with a circular hole subjected to an axial uniform tension in the x direction, by the use of Conformal Transformation, predicting that the location of the maximum stress around the hole could greatly deviate from the cross point with the y axis.

These findings are verified by the experimental results and Finite Element analysis conducted for Carbon/Epoxy angle-ply laminates having bias angles of 30°, 45° and 60°.

INTRODUCTION

Intrinsically the same but different form of various formulae for tangential stress distribution around a circular hole of the infinite orthotropic plate subjected to uni-axial tension in the direction of an elastic axis had been previously given by several investigators, Lekhnitskii S.G. (1), Savin G.N. (2), Green A.E.-Taylor G.I. (3), Ikeda K. (4) and Washizu K. (5), through different mathematical approaches with each other. The experimental study on this problem for orthotropic plates by the use of Photo-Elasticity method was conducted first by Hayashi T. (6), indicating that the experimental results of stress distribution around the hole agreed well with that calculated by the above formulae.

Then, the orthotropic plates used in these theoretical and experimental researches were in most cases the cross-ply laminates made of veneer or GFRP sheets having positive values of g, which is a parameter of orthotropy previously introduced by Ikeda (4) with reference to x and y axes taken along the bisectors of the included angle by a pair of fiber directions shown in Fig.1.

The previous papers cited above, however, had not made any concrete analyses on the stress distribution problem of the orthotropic plates having negative value of g. Recently, the stress concentration problems around a circular

hole of rectangular angle-ply laminates subjected to a uniform extension in the x direction have been numerically solved by using Finite Element method (7), (8) and also experimentally investigated by the Photo-Elasticity method (9), exhibiting that the maximum tangential stress around a circular hole does not always appear at the cross point with the y axis.

Fig.1 Angle-ply laminate with a circular hole under uniform tension in x direction

Then, for the purpose of study on these unusual stress distribution theoretically, an analysis is conducted for an infinite angle-ply laminate having a negative value of g in this paper, giving a formula to the tangential stress around a circular hole and also stresses in the region apart from the hole compared with the experimental results together with numerical results obtained by Finite Element method for Carbon/Epoxy finite angle-ply laminates.

ANALYSIS

Basic Equations

The compatibility equation for orthotropic plate is generally given by

$$e^2 F_{,xxxx} + e(2+g)F_{,xxyy} + F_{,yyyy} = 0 \tag{1}$$

where F denotes Airy's stress function and

$$e^2 = E_x/E_y, \quad g = \sqrt{E_x E_y}/G_{xy} - 2(1 + \sqrt{\nu_x \nu_y}) \tag{2}$$

The value of g is usually positive for cross-ply laminates but could be often negative for angle-ply laminates within a limited range of bias angle, α . For an extreme case of a laminated biased composite sheet of inextensible fiber reinforced rubber layers, g becomes -4 irrespective of bias angle, because the elastic moduli of this laminate are previously given as G_{xy} tends to infinity, $\nu_x = \cot^2 \alpha$, $\nu_y = \tan^2 \alpha$ and $e^2 = \cot^4 \alpha$ by the first author (10), from which Eq.(1) can be transformed as

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} - \tan^2 \alpha \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}\right)^2 F = 0 \tag{3}$$

which is the bi-hyperbolic equation. In another extreme case of isotropy, g takes zero as easily seen, and Eq.(1) yields the bi-harmonic equation as

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}\right)^2 F = 0 \tag{4}$$

Various angle-ply laminates could thus take negative values of g limited by -4 for each definite range of bias angle depending on the constituent fiber and matrix as shown in Fig.2.

Fig.2 Variation of "g" value of various angle-ply laminates as functions of bias angle, α

Following the Ikeda's theory (4), Eq.(1) can be generally dissolved as

$$(\Lambda_1 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2})(\Lambda_2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2})F = 0 \tag{5}$$

where and

$$\Lambda_1^2 \Lambda_2^2 = e^2, \quad \Lambda_1^2 + \Lambda_2^2 = e(2+g) \tag{6}$$

$$\Lambda_1 = k_1 + k_2, \quad \Lambda_2 = k_1 - k_2 \tag{7}$$

$$k_1 = \sqrt{e + eg/4}, \quad k_2 = \sqrt{eg/4}$$

When g is positive, Λ_1 and Λ_2 are both real and the dual complex coordinates, z_1 and z_2 , can be defined by

$$z_1 = x + i\Lambda_1 y, \quad z_2 = x + i\Lambda_2 y \quad (8)$$

nevertheless, for negative value of g existing between 0 and -4 , Λ_1 and Λ_2 become complex and the dual coordinates should be expressed by

$$z_1 = x + \lambda_1 y + i\mu y, \quad z_2 = x + \lambda_2 y + i\mu y \quad (9)$$

where

$$-\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \sqrt{e\bar{g}}/2, \quad \mu = \sqrt{e(4-\bar{g})}/2, \quad \bar{g} = -g > 0 \quad (10)$$

General solution of Eq.(5) is given by

$$F = \text{Re}[F_1(z_1) + F_2(z_2)] \quad (11)$$

and the stress components are thus expressed as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_x = F_{,yy} &= \text{Re}[F_1''(z_1)(\lambda_1 + i\mu)^2 + F_2''(z_2)(\lambda_2 + i\mu)^2] \\ \sigma_y = F_{,xx} &= \text{Re}[F_1''(z_1) + F_2''(z_2)] \\ \tau_{xy} = -F_{,xy} &= -\text{Re}[F_1''(z_1)(\lambda_1 + i\mu) + F_2''(z_2)(\lambda_2 + i\mu)] \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Stress Free Conditions Along The Hole Periphery

The free boundary conditions along the periphery of the hole are written by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial F}{\partial x} &= \text{Re}[F_1'(z_1) + F_2'(z_2)] = 0 \\ \frac{\partial F}{\partial y} &= \text{Re}[F_1'(z_1)(\lambda_1 + i\mu) + F_2'(z_2)(\lambda_2 + i\mu)] = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Eliminating $\overline{F_1'(z_1)}$ and $\overline{F_2'(z_2)}$ from Eq.(13), we obtain the following equations

$$\begin{aligned} (\lambda_1 + i\mu)F_1'(z_1) + i\mu F_2'(z_2) + \lambda_1 \overline{F_1'(z_1)} &= 0 \\ i\mu F_1'(z_1) - (\lambda_1 - i\mu)F_2'(z_2) - \lambda_1 \overline{F_2'(z_2)} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where the over line denotes to be conjugate.

Rotation

The angle of rotation, ω , is given as follows, with the use of displacement functions of u and v in x and y directions respectively

$$\omega = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) \quad (15)$$

Using the Hooke's law as

$$E_x \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \sigma_x - \nu_x \sigma_y, \quad E_y \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = \sigma_y - \nu_y \sigma_x \quad (16)$$

and further Eq.(12), we can obtain following expressions for u and v

$$\begin{aligned} E_x u &= \text{Re}[F_1(z_1)\{(\lambda_1 + i\mu)^2 + \nu_x\} + F_2(z_2)\{(\lambda_2 + i\mu)^2 - \nu_x\}] \\ E_x v &= \text{Re}[F_1(z_1) \frac{\{e^2 - \nu_x(\lambda_1 + i\mu)^2\}}{\lambda_1 + i\mu} + F_2(z_2) \frac{\{e^2 - \nu_x(\lambda_2 + i\mu)^2\}}{\lambda_2 + i\mu}] \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where

$$e^2 = (\lambda_1^2 + \mu^2)^2 \quad (18)$$

which comes from Eq.(10). Substituting Eq.(17) into Eq.(15), we obtain

$$E_x \omega = \frac{1}{2} \text{Re}[F_1''(z_1) \left\{ \frac{e^2}{\lambda_1 + i\mu} - (\lambda_1 + i\mu)^3 \right\} + F_2''(z_2) \left\{ \frac{e^2}{\lambda_2 + i\mu} - (\lambda_2 + i\mu)^3 \right\}] \quad (19)$$

Conformal Transformation

In order to transform the outside domain of the circular hole having radius ,a, in the z (=x+iy) plane into the outside of a unit circle in the ζ (=ξ+iη) plane, we express a pair of dual coordinates, z₁ and z₂, by the following functions of ζ₁ and ζ₂ respectively as

$$z_1 = A_1 \zeta_1 + B_1/\zeta_1, \quad z_2 = A_2 \zeta_2 + B_2/\zeta_2 \tag{20}$$

From the condition that the coordinates of ζ₁=ρ₁exp(iφ₁) and ζ₂=ρ₂exp(iφ₂) coincide with the unit circle in ζ plane, when ρ₁=ρ₂=1 and φ₁=φ₂, we obtain

$$A_k = \frac{a}{2} [(1 + \mu) - i\lambda_k], \quad B_k = \frac{a}{2} [(1 - \mu) + i\lambda_k], \quad (k = 1, 2) \tag{21}$$

Figure 3(a) shows the transformed curves in z plane by Eq.(20) corresponding to the unit circle together with coordinate axes of ξ and η in ζ plane, while Fig.3(b) shows inverse curves in ζ plane corresponding the circular hole and the coordinate axes of x and y in z plane.

Determination of Stress Functions

Assuming the following expressions for F₁'(z₁) and F₂'(z₂)

$$F_1'(z_1) = \phi(\zeta_1) = a_1 \zeta_1 + a_0 + \frac{a-1}{\zeta_1} + \frac{a-2}{\zeta_1^2} + \dots$$

$$F_2'(z_2) = \psi(\zeta_2) = b_1 \zeta_2 + b_0 + \frac{b-1}{\zeta_2} + \frac{b-2}{\zeta_2^2} + \dots \tag{22}$$

and putting these into Eq.(14), we get

$$(\lambda_1 + i\mu)\phi(\sigma) + i\mu\psi(\sigma) + \lambda_1 \bar{\phi}(1/\sigma) = 0$$

$$i\mu\phi(\sigma) - (\lambda_1 - i\mu)\psi(\sigma) - \lambda_1 \bar{\psi}(1/\sigma) = 0 \tag{23}$$

where σ denotes the complex coordinate of a point lying on the unit circle in ζ plane and is given by exp(iθ).

Fig.3 Conformal transformation between z-plane and ζ-plane

Multiplying the both sides of Eq.(23) by (1/2πi)dσ/(σ-ζ), where |ζ|>1, and integrating it along the circumference of the unit circle with consideration of the following relations as

$$\frac{1}{2\pi i} \oint \phi(\sigma) \frac{d\sigma}{\sigma - \zeta} = -\phi(\zeta) + a_1 \zeta + a_0, \quad \frac{1}{2\pi i} \oint \phi(\sigma) \frac{d\sigma}{\sigma - \zeta} = -\bar{a}_1 \frac{1}{\zeta} \tag{24}$$

we obtain

$$\phi(\zeta_1) = a_0 + a_1 \zeta_1 - \{\lambda_1 \bar{a}_1 - i\mu(\bar{a}_1 + \bar{b}_1)\} / \lambda_1 \zeta_1$$

$$\psi(\zeta_2) = b_0 + b_1 \zeta_2 - \{\lambda_1 \bar{b}_1 + i\mu(\bar{a}_1 + \bar{b}_1)\} / \lambda_1 \zeta_2 \tag{25}$$

Then, we have

$$F_1''(z_1) = \frac{a_1 + \{\lambda_1 \bar{a}_1 - i\mu(\bar{a}_1 + \bar{b}_1)\} / \lambda_1 \zeta_1^2}{A_1 - B_1/\zeta_1^2}$$

$$F_2''(z_2) = \frac{b_1 + \{\lambda_1 \bar{b}_1 + i\mu(\bar{a}_1 + \bar{b}_1)\} / \lambda_1 \zeta_2^2}{A_2 - B_2/\zeta_2^2} \tag{26}$$

where a₁ and b₁ can be determined from the boundary conditions at infinity of

$$[\sigma_x]_\infty = p, \quad [\sigma_y]_\infty = [\tau_{xy}]_\infty = [\omega]_\infty = 0 \tag{27}$$

as follows.

$$a_1 = \frac{ap}{8\lambda_1\mu} \{-\lambda_1 - i(1+\mu)\}, \quad b_1 = \frac{ap}{8\lambda_2\mu} \{-\lambda_2 - i(1+\mu)\} \quad (28)$$

Stress Components

Putting Eq.(26) into Eq.(12), we obtain the relative stress components as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\sigma_x}{p} &= 1 - \sum_k \frac{1}{k} \frac{1}{\lambda_k} \operatorname{Im} \left[\frac{(\lambda_k + i\mu)^2}{(1+\mu - i\lambda_k)\zeta_k^2 - (1-\mu + i\lambda_k)} \right] \\ \frac{\sigma_y}{p} &= - \sum_k \frac{1}{k} \frac{1}{\lambda_k} \operatorname{Im} \left[\frac{1}{(1+\mu - i\lambda_k)\zeta_k^2 - (1-\mu + i\lambda_k)} \right] \\ \frac{\tau_{xy}}{p} &= \sum_k \frac{1}{k} \frac{1}{\lambda_k} \operatorname{Im} \left[\frac{\lambda_k + i\mu}{(1+\mu - i\lambda_k)\zeta_k^2 - (1-\mu + i\lambda_k)} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

The tangential stress around the hole, σ_θ , can be obtained by taking $\zeta_k = \exp(i\theta)$ and $\sigma_\theta = \sigma_x + \sigma_y$ at the hole boundary into consideration as follows.

$$\frac{\sigma_\theta}{p} = 1 - \sum_k \frac{(\lambda_k^2 + \mu^2 + 1)(1 + \cos 2\theta) - 2\mu(1 - \cos 2\theta) + (\mu - 1)/\lambda_k \{ \lambda_k^2 + (1+\mu)^2 \} \sin 2\theta}{2\{1 - \cos 2\theta + (\lambda_k^2 + \mu^2)(1 + \cos 2\theta) - 2\lambda_k \sin 2\theta\}} \quad (30)$$

It should be noted that the tangential stress, σ_θ , of Eq.(30) is proved to coincide with the Ikeda's formula (4) which was given as

$$\frac{\sigma_\theta}{p} = 1 + \frac{\Lambda_1 + 1}{\Lambda_2 - \Lambda_1} \frac{(\Lambda_1 - 1)^2 + (\Lambda_1^2 - 1)\cos 2\theta}{(\Lambda_1^2 + 1) + (\Lambda_1^2 - 1)\cos 2\theta} - \frac{\Lambda_2 + 1}{\Lambda_2 - \Lambda_1} \frac{(\Lambda_2 - 1)^2 + (\Lambda_2^2 - 1)\cos 2\theta}{(\Lambda_2^2 + 1) + (\Lambda_2^2 - 1)\cos 2\theta} \quad (31)$$

by putting the following relations into Eq.(30).

$$\Lambda_1 = \mu + i\lambda_1, \quad \Lambda_2 = \mu + i\lambda_2 \quad (32)$$

Green-Taylor's formula (3);

$$\frac{\sigma_\theta}{p} = \frac{(1+\gamma_1)(1+\gamma_2)(1+\gamma_1+\gamma_2-\gamma_1\gamma_2-2\cos 2\theta)}{(1+\gamma_1)^2-2\gamma_1\cos 2\theta}(1+\gamma_2^2-2\gamma_2\cos 2\theta) \quad (33)$$

where

$$\gamma_1 = \frac{t_1 - 1}{t_1 + 1}, \quad \gamma_2 = \frac{t_2 - 1}{t_2 + 1}, \quad t_1 = \frac{1}{\Lambda_1}, \quad t_2 = \frac{1}{\Lambda_2} \quad (34)$$

is also shown to agree with Eq.(30) by the same replacement of Eq.(32).

Stresses Apart From The Hole

The conformal transformation given by Eq.(20) yields rather complicated correspondence between z and ζ planes when g is negative as illustrated in Fig.3, in contrast to the situation that the coordinate axes of x and y directly correspond to these of ξ and η respectively when g is positive. Separating the real and imaginary parts of Eq.(20) by the use of Eq.(9), we can obtain the following relations.

$$\begin{aligned} x + \lambda ky &= \frac{a}{2} [\rho_k \{ (1+\mu) \cos \phi_k + \lambda_k \sin \phi_k \} + \frac{1}{\rho_k} \{ (1-\mu) \cos \phi_k + \lambda_k \sin \phi_k \}] \\ \mu y &= \frac{a}{2} [\rho_k \{ (1+\mu) \sin \phi_k - \lambda_k \cos \phi_k \} + \frac{1}{\rho_k} \{ \lambda_k \cos \phi_k - (1-\mu) \sin \phi_k \}] \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

Elimination of ϕ_k from Eq.(35) leads to

$$A_k X^2 + 2B_k XY + C_k Y^2 = D_k, \quad (k = 1, 2) \quad (36)$$

where $X = x/a$, $Y = y/a$ and

$$\begin{aligned} A_k &= n_k^2 + s_k^2, & B_k &= n_k(n_k \lambda_k - r_k \mu) + s_k(s_k \lambda_k - m_k \mu) \\ C_k &= \lambda_k^2(n_k^2 + s_k^2) + \mu^2(m_k^2 + r_k^2), & D_k &= (r_k s_k - m_k n_k)^2 / 4 \\ m_k &= \rho_k(1+\mu) + (1-\mu)/\rho_k, & n_k &= \rho_k(1+\mu) - (1-\mu)/\rho_k \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

$$r_k = \lambda_k(\rho_k + 1/\rho_k), \quad s_k = \lambda_k(-\rho_k + 1/\rho_k)$$

Elimination of ρ_k from Eq.(35) yields

$$\phi_k = \tan^{-1} \frac{Xs_k - Y(m_k \mu - s_k \lambda_k)}{Y(r_k \mu - n_k \lambda_k) - Xn_k} \quad (38)$$

For the given values of x and y , generally, each ρ_k ($k=1, 2$) can be obtained by solving Eq.(36) and the corresponding ϕ_k is determined from Eq.(38) and then stress components are calculated by Eq.(29). In the special cases of x or y being zero, the relations of $\rho_2 = \rho_1$ and $\phi_2 = -\phi_1$ are found by taking the relation of $\lambda_2 = -\lambda_1$ into consideration.

NUMERICAL CALCULATION

Numerical Examples

The elastic properties of angle-ply laminates of Glass/Epoxy, Carbon/Epoxy and Polyester/Rubber, each having three kinds of bias angle; $\alpha = 30^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 60° , are listed in Table 1. The resulting σ_θ distribution around the circular hole together with σ_x along x and y axes are illustrated in Fig.4(A, B and C).

Table 1 Numerical Examples

α	Glass/Epoxy			Carbon/Epoxy			Polyester/Rubber		
	30°	45°	60°	30°	45°	60°	30°	45°	60°
E_x (GPa)	21.00	15.00	11.00	30.00	9.231	7.732	0.03921	0.00741	0.00589
E_y (GPa)	11.00	15.00	21.00	7.732	9.231	30.00	0.00589	0.00741	0.03921
ν_x	0.610	0.540	0.320	1.400	0.846	0.361	2.266	0.953	0.341
ν_y	0.320	0.540	0.610	0.361	0.846	1.400	0.341	0.953	2.266
G_{xy} (GPa)	8.500	10.00	8.500	19.38	25.00	19.38	0.05672	0.07500	0.05672
e	1.382	1.000	0.724	1.970	1.000	0.508	2.580	1.000	0.388
g	-1.096	-1.580	-1.096	-2.636	-3.323	-2.636	-3.490	-3.807	-3.590

Fig.4 Distribution of tangential stress σ_θ around a circular hole and σ_x along x and y axes for A: Glass/Epoxy(30°), B: Carbon/Epoxy(45°) and C: Polyester/Rubber(60°)

It should be noted here that the location of the maximum tangential stress, $\sigma_{\theta \max}$, deviates significantly from $\theta = 90^\circ$ along with the maximum increase of \bar{g} and α , but insistently remains at $\theta = 90^\circ$ for \bar{g} being smaller than about 1.6. Figure 5 depicts a map of principal stress directions for Carbon/Epoxy(45°) calculated by

$$\beta = \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} \frac{2\tau_{xy}}{\sigma_x - \sigma_y} \quad (39)$$

where β is the inclination angle of the principal stress direction and the stress components are obtained from the preceding analysis by the use of electronic

computer.

Finite Element Analysis

For the purpose of comparing with the analytical and the experimental results, a Finite Element analysis is conducted for the same kinds of angle-ply laminates as these listed in Table 1, having the dimensions of $240 \times 240 \text{ mm}^2$ and the hole radius of 40 mm. A quadrant of the laminate was divided by 86 number of triangular elements including 56 knot points as shown in Figs.6 and 7.

Figure 6 illustrates the deformation of Carbon/Epoxy(45°) laminate under the uniform tensile stress, $p = 0.375 \text{ MPa}$. Figure 7 depicts a map of principal stress direction of the same laminate as Fig.6, predicting an analogous trend with Fig.5 in spite of different size between the two laminates.

Fig.5 Map of the principal stress direction for Carbon/Epoxy(45°) infinite laminate

Fig.6 Deformation of finite Carbon/Epoxy (45°) angle-ply laminate calculated by Finite Element method

Fig.7 Principal stress directions of finite Carbon/Epoxy(45°) angle-ply laminate due to Finite Element analysis

COMPARISON BETWEEN ANALYTICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Experiment

Strain measuring experiments were conducted for three specimens of Carbon/Epoxy laminates with bias angles of 30° , 45° and 60° , one of which is shown in Fig.8. Each specimen has the same size of 380 mm length, 227.5 mm width, 0.5 mm thickness and 30 mm hole radius. The both ends of each specimen are sandwiched by pairs of steel plates as to transmit the uniform tensile stress across the width near the ends.

Strain gages of $2 \sim 5 \text{ mm}$ gage lengths were adequately set up on both sides of each specimen, in the tangential direction around the hole and in the x direction along x and y axes. The stress components were calculated from the orthotropic elasticity laws by using the numerical values of elastic

Fig.8 Test specimen of Carbon/Epoxy(30°) angle-ply laminate

moduli listed in Table 1, which were obtained through the separated experiments for each specimen.

Comparison With Test Results

Figure 9 shows the distribution of relative stresses of σ_{θ}/p around a circular hole and σ_x/p along x and y axes for Carbon/Epoxy laminates, having bias angles of 30° , 45° and 60° , under a uniform tensile stress, p, comparing the theoretical curves depicted by full lines with the corresponding experimental results denoted by black points as \bullet , \blacksquare and \blacktriangle and the results of Finite Element analysis designated by white points as \circ , \square and Δ .

Good agreement can be observed equally in these figures between the experimental and Finite Element results, partly because both results were obtained for a little different but commonly finite size of laminates. Furthermore, these points seem to support roughly the theoretical curves which were obtained for infinite laminates, clearly indicating an analogous trend that the location of the maximum tangential stress around the hole deviates significantly from the position of $\theta = 90^\circ$.

Fig.9 Theoretical stress distribution compared with the results of experiments and FEM analysis for Carbon/Epoxy angle-ply laminates

CONCLUSION

The stress distribution of angle-ply laminate with a circular hole under uni-axial tension is analyzed by using the Conformal Transformation, exhibiting that the calculated results agree well with the experimental and FEM results.

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